

A Review of the Reproducibility Ecosystem in Computational Science

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Abstract

This scoping review maps the computational reproducibility ecosystem across four facets: (1) foundations and definitions; (2) conceptual frameworks and principles (e.g., FAIR, PRIMAD); (3) best practices and publishing; and (4) tools and platforms (e.g., containerisation, workflow systems, version control, notebooks). We classify tools using PRIMAD dimensions: **P**latform, **R**esearch Objective, **I**mplementation, **M**ethod, **A**ctor, and **D**ata, showing how different stages of computational studies require distinct support. Evidence converges on a socio-technical insight: reproducibility takes a village. Infrastructure is necessary but insufficient without aligned incentives, policies, training, and community culture.

1 Introduction

Computers have become a routine, low-cost “laboratory” that complements theory and hands-on experiments in every branch of science. In physical science, machine learning solvers now stand in for wind tunnels or accelerators by solving the governing partial differential equations thousands of times faster (Brunton & Kutz, 2023), so physicists can explore whole design spaces on a laptop before building anything in steel. In the life science, DeepMind’s AlphaFold shows how the same idea turns crystallography into a keyboard task: the software can predict the 3D shape of most known proteins in minutes (Tunyasuvunakool et al., 2021), accelerating drug discovery and enzyme engineering without a single wet lab experiment. In social science,

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researchers run vast agent-based worlds (Gao et al., 2024), now populated with large language model “citizens”, to test how rumours spread, how epidemics respond to lockdown rules, or how taxes alter inequality. These computational experiments are powered by a revolution in scientific methodology, drawing on the massive, explorable datasets of the Fourth Paradigm (Hey, 2009) and the transformative analytical capabilities of the AI-driven Fifth Paradigm (Ioannidis, 2024), give scientists fine control over variables, automatic provenance records, and shareable digital artifacts. However, despite these advantages, achieving computational reproducibility, a simple premise in theory, remains notoriously difficult in practice (Ziemann et al., 2023).

The issue of reproducibility came to the forefront after a landmark 2016 *Nature* survey revealed that over 70% had encountered difficulties replicating another scientist’s experiments, with more than half unable even to reproduce their work, widely referred to as the “reproducibility crisis” (Baker, 2016). Computational reproducibility is defined by the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM, 2019) as “obtaining consistent computational results using the same input data, computational steps, methods, and code, and conditions of analysis.” Despite growing awareness, a 2024 survey in *PLOS Biology* found that 72% of biomedical researchers still believe their field faces a crisis, with “pressure to publish” cited as a leading cause (Cobey et al., 2024).

In response, numerous initiatives have been launched within the scholarly community to address reproducibility from various perspectives, aiming to foster greater transparency. The primary purpose of this literature review is to examine the current state of knowledge on computational reproducibility in computational science. Recognising that the reproducibility “take a village” of stakeholders, infrastructures, and practices (Borgman & Bourne, 2022), no single researcher, guideline, tool, or framework can address the challenge in isolation. Accordingly, this review aims to highlight both the theoretical foundations and practical implementations that enhance reproducibility in the computational sciences, organised into four thematic sections as illustrated in Figure 1, which outlines the structure of this review. These sections include Foundations of Reproducibility, Conceptual Frameworks and Principles, Best Practices and Publishing, and Tools and Platforms Supporting Reproducibility.

Figure 1. The Paper Review Roadmap. The figure outlines the four thematic pillars of this review: Foundations of Reproducibility, Frameworks and Principles, Best Practices and Publishing, and Tools and Platforms.

The first section, **Foundations of Reproducibility in Computational Science**, delves into the historical context of the reproducibility debate and clarifies key concepts. This is crucial, as even today there is no universally accepted definition of 'reproducibility,' with terminology varying widely across disciplines (Heyard et al., 2025). The second section, **Conceptual Frameworks and Principles**, examines the intellectual architecture designed to support reproducible science. It explores established models and guidelines, such as the FAIR Data Principles, the PRIMAD Model, the Research Object paradigm, and various provenance models, which collectively provide a standardized language and structure for reproducible workflows.

The third section, **Best Practices and Publishing**, transitions from theory to practice by discussing prominent initiatives and community-driven standards that promote transparency. This section highlights the critical role of journals and funding agencies in fostering a culture change toward open science and examines influential community resources that provide practical guidance for

researchers. Finally, the fourth section, **Tools and Platforms** Supporting Reproducibility, surveys the technical scaffolding that makes reproducible research feasible. It presents a range of practical solutions, including metadata standards, containerization, workflow management systems, version control, and computational notebooks, that facilitate reproducible workflows across diverse computational domains.

2 Scoping Review Methodology and Limitations

This paper adopts a scoping review approach, providing a brief historical overview of reproducibility. It then presents some of the most cited frameworks, principles, guidelines, and best practices. Later, it surveys tools across the research lifecycle, organised by the PRIMAD dimensions (Platform, Research Objective, Implementation, Method, Actor, Data; see Table 2).

The search relied on Google Scholar (and Google) as the discovery interface primarily in May 2025, with additional queries conducted by the first author during their PhD in 2023–2024. We combined a core stem for reproducibility with section-specific terms. The core term was reproduc*. Conceptual work used (framework OR model OR principle* OR ontology); practices/policy used (policy OR checklist OR publishing); tools used (workflow OR container OR notebook OR "metadata package"). To improve coverage within the Google-only constraint, we applied backward and forward snowballing from seed papers and standards identified in search results. We also targeted official standards/specification sites surfaced via Google (e.g., standards bodies, community consortia). Records were deduplicated and screened at the title/abstract level against the eligibility criteria. Full-text screening was conducted for borderline cases and for all candidate standards and tools. Reasons for exclusion at full text were recorded (e.g., out of scope; non-computational; not a framework/standard/tool).

The review prioritized concision by applying a rule-based sampling within each content bucket (frameworks/principles; standards/specifications; tools/platforms): we included the most-cited and/or field-defining sources. Additionally, we utilised the AI tools (specifically ChatGPT) for brainstorming synonyms and query variants. All retrieval, screening, and data extraction were carried out manually, and no LLM output was accepted as a source without verification against

primary materials. This review is limited by its reliance on Google/Google Scholar searches conducted in May 2025 and by rule-based sampling for concision, which may omit relevant materials outside this window or indexing scope.

3 Foundations of Reproducibility in Computational Science

“Computation fills in a gap between theory and experiment,” said David Ham, a computational scientist at Imperial College London (Houstis et al., 2000).

Computational science is an interdisciplinary field that employs mathematical models, numerical methods, and computer simulations to investigate and solve complex scientific and engineering problems (Houstis et al., 2000). In recent years, computational experiments have evolved to provide a flexible framework to model, analyse, and optimise complex cyber-physical-social systems through artificial societies and iterative feedback loops (Xue et al., 2022). By integrating advanced technologies such as digital twins and reinforcement learning, computational experiments enable researchers to conduct controlled, repeatable studies in virtual environments, facilitating causal exploration and testing interventions that would be infeasible in real-world scenarios.

As computational methods have become more powerful and intricate, scientists increasingly recognize that reproducibility—the ability to obtain consistent results using the original data and code—is not guaranteed by traditional publications alone (Bechhofer et al., 2010). In the early 1990s, Jon Claerbout defined “reproducible research” in its modern sense, emphasizing that published articles should be accompanied by complete code and datasets used to produce results (Claerbout and Karrenbach 1992). Throughout the 1990s and early 2000s, the theoretical foundation for computational reproducibility strengthened significantly (Lieberman, 2015). Through the “Reproducibility Crisis” (Baker, 2016), the scientific community has investigated and addressed reproducibility challenges in diverse domains. Later, this historical push established transparency and reproducibility as essential components of credible computational science

from 2016 to the present. The following two sections provide an overview of these investigations across various scientific disciplines and delve into the key concepts and definitions that underpin reproducibility.

3.1 Historical Evolution

Over the past decade has been a growing recognition of the reproducibility crisis affecting multiple scientific disciplines, the Baker’s survey (2016) indicated that no field has been completely immune, though physicists and chemists expressed somewhat higher confidence in their findings (Kulkarni, 2016). Consequently, reproducibility profoundly influences a wide range of disciplines, continuously reshaping research practices across the formal sciences, natural sciences (including both physical and life sciences), and social sciences. For classification purposes within this work, the scientific disciplines will follow the categorization of Cohen (2021), as shown in Table 1.

Science	Formal	Natural		Social
		Physical	Life	
Foundation	Logic, <i>Mathematics</i> , <i>Statistics</i>	Physics, Chemistry, Earth Science, Astronomy	Biology	Economics, Psychology, Sociology
Applied	Computer Science	Engineering, Agriculture	<i>Medicine</i> , Pharmacology	Business, Administration, Pedagogy

Table 1. Classification of Scientific Disciplines Adapted from Cohen (2021): *The University and its Boundaries: Thriving or Surviving*, Cohen (2021).

In **computer science**, reproducibility is frequently compromised by limited sharing of code and data, methodological ambiguity, and dependency on highly specific software and hardware environments. Collberg and Proebsting, (2016) assessed research papers in computer systems, finding that only approximately 32% of published results were reproducible without author assistance. Even with active collaboration from authors, reproducibility rates rose only to around 54%. Reviewing 400 artificial intelligence (AI) papers from major conferences showed similar trends: merely 6% provided the full source code, about 30% included test datasets, and around 54% offered only pseudocode (Hutson, 2018). Gundersen and Kjensmo (2018) further validate

their prediction that current documentation practices at leading AI conferences result in most reported research findings being irreproducible, indicating that no papers achieve full reproducibility. A recent replication study of 30 highly cited AI papers found that only 50% were reproducible to some extent, revealing a significant correlation between reproducibility and the quality of data documentation (Gundersen et al., 2025).

The **life sciences** have historically faced significant reproducibility challenges. Ioannidis et al., (2005) seminal critique, "Why most published research findings are false", underscored pervasive biases, methodological weaknesses, and selective reporting prevalent in biomedical research. Similarly, (Pusztai et al., 2013) highlighted the challenges related to inadequate sample sizes, publication bias favoring positive outcomes, and the complexity of replicating complex biological phenomena under varied laboratory conditions. The Reproducibility Project: Cancer Biology (Errington et al., 2021) reinforced these concerns, demonstrating extensive replication failures in cancer research.

Although **physical sciences** have traditionally been considered robust regarding reproducibility, Astronomers, for example, have historically faced reproducibility challenges in replicating experimental results, despite modern astronomy embracing fully digital workflows, illustrating that digitization alone does not fully resolve issues related to reproducibility (Ruiz et al., 2012). (Allen et al., 2018) found that only three out of five astrophysics papers published in 2015 provided accessible source code. In computational fluid dynamics (CFD), Mesnard and Barba (2017) specifically highlighted severe reproducibility difficulties where three years of dedicated work were required to successfully replicate only four computational studies. More broadly, engineering fields frequently encounter problems in replicating studies due to highly specialized experimental setups, computational environments, and methodological details not thoroughly documented in original research publications (National Academies of Sciences, 2019).

The **social sciences** have also figured prominently in reproducibility discussions, particularly in psychology and economics. (Open Science Collaboration, 2015) documented a strikingly low replication rate of 36% for 100 influential psychological studies. In a review of 250 articles published between 2014 and 2017, Hardwicke et al. (2020) found limited use of transparent and

reproducible research practices across the broader social sciences, underscoring persistent challenges. In economics, Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System et al. (2015) similarly showed that only about 33–49% of empirical papers could be successfully replicated, even with direct assistance from the original authors. (Camerer et al., 2018) further emphasized reproducibility issues by highlighting widespread inflated effect sizes and limited robustness of findings across various social science disciplines.

3.2 Definitions and Key Concepts

Reproducibility is a cornerstone of scientific inquiry, validating research findings and enabling other researchers to build upon them with confidence (House of Commons, 2023). In computational science, computational reproducibility specifically refers to the ability to replicate the same results when reusing the original data, code, and analytical conditions (NASEM, 2019). This means that an independent researcher, or even the original investigator at a later time, can re-execute the software and procedures on the specified dataset and reliably obtain the published outcomes (Liu & Salganik, 2019). Achieving repeatability requires a commitment to transparency and rigorous documentation, including clear accounts of data preprocessing steps, algorithms, parameters, and software environments. Notably, in the previous discussion, the “R-words”—*reproduce*, *replicate*, *repeat*, and *re-execute*—figure prominently in the discourse on reproducibility. In the academic and technical literature, there is a marked tendency to use these “R-words” interchangeably (De Roure, 2014). Consequently, various scholars and organizations have attempted to unify and standardize these terms, although complete consensus remains intangible.

The term reproducible research emerged in the early 1990s from geophysicist Jon Claerbout (Claerbout & Karrenbach, 1992). Around the same time, social scientist Gary King (King, 1995) advocated for a “replication standard,” calling on researchers to provide “sufficient information... with which to understand, evaluate, and build upon a prior work.” Essentially, both Claerbout and King pressed for sharing data and methods so that others could verify or extend research, results. (Buckheit & Donoho, 1995) reinforced Claerbout’s messages that computational scientists should engage in “really reproducible” research and that true reproducibility requires

distributing “a whole computing environment aimed at allowing others to easily reproduce the figures in our articles”. These early contributions laid the groundwork for reproducibility as a cornerstone of credible science across disciplines.

By the late 2000s, the reproducible research movement gained momentum in computational fields. Donoho et al. (2009) Explicitly defined reproducible computational research as research in which “all details of the computation—code and data—are made conveniently available to others”. In practice, this means that an independent researcher could use the original authors’ code and dataset to obtain the same results. In the life sciences and data science communities, reproducibility quickly became the minimum standard for evaluating scientific claims when full independent replication was impractical (Peng, 2011). (Stodden, 2014) further emphasizes that reproducibility is a multi-faceted notion and identifies at least three forms: computational reproducibility (providing details of code, software and hardware so computational analyses can be repeated), empirical reproducibility (making available the data and experimental protocols so empirical observations can be reproduced), and statistical reproducibility (disclosing statistical design and modelling choices, e.g. through preregistration, so that analyses are unbiased and verifiable).

Despite general agreement on its importance, terminology around reproducibility varies across disciplines, occasionally confusing. Plesser (2017), Barba (2018), and Gundersen (2021) had each tackled these semantic challenges from different angles. **Barba (2018)** highlighted how terminologies diverge across disciplines, emphasizing the Claerbout and Karrenbach (1992), Donoho et al. (2009) and Peng (2011) conventions in computational science where reproducibility means obtaining the same results using the same data and code, while *replication* refers to confirming results independently. She criticized the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) for initially reversing the meanings of “reproducibility” and “replication” in its 2016 guidelines². Recognizing this discrepancy, the ACM updated its terminology in 2020 to align more closely with standard scientific usage³. **Plesser (2017)** traced the historical divergence,

² <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-badging>

³ <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

noting that fields like metrology and experimental science define reproducibility as independent confirmation under varied conditions, contrasting with Claerbout's computational model. Consequently, he supported Goodman et al. (2016) in proposing more precise labels: "methods reproducibility," "results reproducibility", and "inferential reproducibility". **Gundersen's (2021)** reproducibility definitions survey identified 11 factors influencing reproducibility: investigators, science theory, hypothesis, experimental procedure, implementation, ancillary Software, hardware, data, outcome, analysis, and interpretation. Each factor was characterised by whether it remained the same, changed, or was unspecified in the definitions under review. Moreover, he sidestepped the reproducibility-versus-replication division by defining reproducibility simply as the ability for independent researchers to arrive at the same conclusions using shared documentation, while distinguishing "repeatability" as same-team repetition.

Taken together, these contributions underscore that reproducibility is not an all-or-nothing concept but a spectrum. Plesser (2017) offered a historical review of 18 definitions of reproducibility published between 1992 and 2017, while Lorena (2018) categorised 43 definitions into distinctions between reproducibility and replicability. Additionally, Gundersen (2021) advanced the understanding of computational reproducibility in a systematic survey of 35 scholarly sources (1992–2020), highlighting the absence of a single, universally agreed-upon definition for computational reproducibility. Although consistent terminology is helpful for scholarly communication, clarity in naming alone is insufficient to resolve misunderstandings. Instead, definitions must be mapped to a conceptual framework that specifies how reproducibility applies to data, methods, code, and documentation. The PRIMAD model (Freire et al., 2016), discussed in the following section, offers exactly that sort of framework, showing how different reproducibility terms relate to the components of a computational study and, in doing so, providing a more discipline-sensitive approach.

4 Conceptual Frameworks and Principles for Reproducibility

In light of the conceptual diversity surrounding reproducibility, formal frameworks have emerged as essential tools for operationalising it in computational science. The preceding discussion established that reproducibility spans a spectrum of conditions and degrees with no universally agreed-upon definition. To move from conceptual understanding to practice, conceptual clarity must be paired with practical frameworks that guide the implementation of reproducibility tools and best practices in real-world research (discussed in Sections 5 and 6). This section serves as a bridge between the theoretical understanding of reproducibility and the actionable strategies needed to foster it. It introduces several prominent frameworks and approaches that guide reproducible practices. It presents the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), the PRIMAD model (Freire et al., 2016), the Research Object approach (Bechhofer et al., 2010) and provenance models, as well as additional frameworks from recent literature that address specific facets of reproducibility.

4.1 FAIR Data Principles

The FAIR Principles address the lack of clear, universal standards for publishing scientific data, emphasizing that transparent, well-documented, and easily accessible data are vital for ensuring validity, reproducibility, and future discoveries (Wilkinson et al., 2016), Figure 2. The primary goal is not merely to encourage data sharing, but to ensure that data are made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) in ways that enable both humans and machines to locate, interpret, and reapply them. Each FAIR component addresses a distinct dimension of data stewardship. Together, they function as a framework for researchers, data curators, and publishers, promoting transparency throughout the research lifecycle and reusability.

One of FAIR's most notable attributes is its widespread, cross-disciplinary acceptance as a gold standard for scientific data handling (UNESCO, 2021). By remaining agnostic to any specific

software or file format (Mons et al., 2017), the FAIR principles have proven equally applicable to most scientific fields, including computer science (e.g., machine learning; (Samuel et al. 2021), physical science (e.g., astronomy; (O’Toole & Tocknell, 2022)), life science (e.g., biology; (Wolstencroft et al., 2017)), and the social sciences (e.g., economics (Betancort Cabrera et al., 2020)). Their adoption has prompted substantial changes in how research data are managed across academia, industry, and policy (Wilkinson et al., 2019). Nevertheless, implementing the principles in full remains a significant challenge (Kalinin & Skvortsov, 2023; Alharbi et al., 2021; Mons et al., 2020; Jacobsen et al., 2019; Goble et al., 2019), as it requires technical, cultural, educational, and organisational shifts.

Figure 2. The original FAIR Guiding Principles, as published by Wilkinson et al. (2016) and the FAIR Tulip Logo⁴ by Meznah Aloqalaa.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15277862>

4.2 PRIMAD Model

The PRIMAD model offers a foundational framework for computational reproducibility. It was formulated during a Dagstuhl seminar 16321 in 2016⁵, and helps researchers reason about what kind of terminology of reproducibility they are evaluating. Within PRIMAD, one specifies which components are held constant and which are varied in a given reproduction attempt, thereby making explicit the conditions under which results are reproduced. This structured approach directly addresses the confusion caused by the inconsistent use of “R words” (De Roure, 2014). By mapping each term to a distinct combination of fixed and variable components of the experiment, the PRIMAD model disambiguates their meanings.

label	P	R	I	M	A	D		Gain
	Platform	Research Objective	Implementation	Method	Actor	Data		
						Raw data	Parameters	
Repeat	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Determinism
Port	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	Portability across platforms, flexibility
Re-use	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	Apply code in different sitting, Re-purpose
Re-code	(X)	-	X	-	-	-	-	Correctness of implementation, flexibility, adoption, efficiency
Validate	(X)	-	(X)	X	-	(X)	(X)	Correctness of hypothesis, validation via a different approach
Independent x	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	Sufficiency information, independent verification
Parameter Sweep	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	Robustness and Sensitivity
Generalize	-	-	-	-	-	(X)	X	Applicability across different settings

Table 2. The PRIMAD Model for Reproducibility in a Computational Experiment. Each reproducibility label is associated with its gain and the way of achieving it. What dimensions will change X, change accordingly (X), or will not change? Adapted from (Freire et al., 2016).

The model (see Table 2) presents different labels of reproducibility in relation to changing variables, highlighting gains in reproducibility based on which variable is changed in a computational experiment, reflecting reproducibility objectives such as portability, adaptability to other conditions, improved code quality, resource efficiency, flexibility, robustness of findings, and greater transparency. For example, to improve experiment portability, a change is required for the platform in the reproducible experiment. Expanding the adoption of the methodology as

⁵ <https://www.dagstuhl.de/16321>

an advantage will necessitate a different implementation. However, the platform might need to be adjusted accordingly.

The acronym 'PRIMAD' represents the prime variables that can change (or be fixed) during the reproduction of a computational study (Freire et al., 2016).

- **P:** Platform: the execution environment and computational context.
- **R:** Research Objectives or goals of the study.
- **I:** Implementation: the computational code or source code.
- **M:** Methods: the algorithm, pseudocode, and/or methodology that fulfil the study goals.
- **A:** Actor: the people who contribute to the study.
- **D:** Data: input data and parameter values of the source code.

The PRIMAD model also incorporates two implicit dimensions: **consistency**, which means that the reproducible results should align with the original study outcomes, and **transparency**, which indicates that the key elements of the research study throughout its life cycle should be transparent, enabling its reproduction.

4.3 Provenance Model

Provenance —the documentation of the origin and history of data and computational processes —is widely recognised as a cornerstone of reproducible research (Moreau, 2011). Capturing provenance information allows scientists to trace which data were used, how they were processed, and who or what was responsible for each step (W3C, 2013; Herschel et al., 2017), thereby enabling others to reproduce and verify computational results and ultimately strengthening the credibility of scientific findings. According to (Herschel et al., 2017), provenance can be classified by type (data, workflow, metadata) and by goal (understandability, reproducibility, quality), with another critical dimension being the form it takes: prospective provenance describes the static structure of a workflow, retrospective provenance documents the detailed execution history, and evolution provenance reflects changes over time.

Over the years, numerous provenance modelling languages have been developed to represent such information in a structured, interoperable way. Early examples include the Open Provenance Model (OPM) (Moreau, 2011) and the Proof/Provenance Markup Language (PML) (da Silva et al., 2006). However, these were later superseded by more recent standards, specifically by W3C PROV⁶. W3C PROV, published as a World Wide Web Consortium Recommendation in 2013, effectively succeeded OPM. It expanded and formalised provenance modelling to improve interoperability and align with other web standards. The PROV family of specifications includes a conceptual data model (PROV-DM), multiple serialisation formats for data exchange, and guidelines for applying provenance in practice, such as PROV-N (a human-readable notation) and PROV-O (an OWL2 ontology mapping the PROV data model to RDF (Resource Description Framework)). At its core, the PROV data model defines three primary classes—Entity, Activity, and Agent—and specifies a rich set of relationships between them (e.g., “wasGeneratedBy,” which links an Entity’s creation to an Activity and “wasDerivedFrom” denotes that an Entity was derived from another Entity). These entities and relationships form a provenance graph that captures the lineage of data. W3C PROV thus provides a robust and flexible backbone for provenance in reproducible research (Johns et al., 2023). Known limitations—such as its stronger emphasis on retrospective over prospective provenance—are being addressed through extensions rather than wholesale replacement (Auge et al., 2023).

4.4 Research Object

Modern computational science increasingly demands a systematic approach to capture all components of a research effort and make them available in one place. Results often rely on a complex array of artifacts (e.g., datasets, software code, documentation, workflows, and more) that are usually distributed across papers, repositories, and websites. While frameworks like FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interpretable and reusable) (Wilkinson et al., 2016) and PRIMAD (Freire et al., 2016) offer guiding principles for improving accessibility and describing facets of computational reproducibility, they do not directly solve the bundling challenge (that is, they

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-overview/>

don't specify how to package data, code, and methods together as one unified object that can be transferred and cited as a whole). Research Objects (RO), as introduced by Bechhofer et al. (2010), fill this gap by providing a semantic encapsulation mechanism for the entire digital research lifecycle. An RO is a coherent, shareable unit that can include primary data, analysis code, documentation, workflow definitions, intermediate results, and relevant metadata. By ensuring that all elements of a computational experiment and its context are aggregated into one package, ROs support reproducibility, facilitate verification, and make research more portable and reusable (Bechhofer et al., 2013).

4.5 Related Frameworks

In addition to FAIR principles, PRIMAD model, provenance models, and the research object approach, several influential frameworks seek to enhance transparency and reproducibility in computational research. This subsection highlights three frameworks notable for their broad relevance and structured approach:

- **Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines** (Nosek et al., 2015; Grant et al., 2025). TOP 2015 Guidelines set out eight modular standards to encourage sharing of data, code, and research materials, thereby incentivizing more transparent practices among authors and journals (Nosek et al., 2015). Noting that the original guidelines lacked an explicit conceptual framework, inviting divergent interpretations of their purpose and scope, Grant et al. (2025) introduce TOP 2025, which articulates a unifying framework centered on the verifiability of empirical claims and informs the guidelines' reorganization, revisions, and recommended use across stakeholders. TOP 2025 reorganizes standards into three distinct categories: Research Practices, Verification Practices and Verification Studies.
- **TRUST Principles** (Lin et al., 2020) emphasize five core qualities of trustworthy digital repositories: Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology. By preserving data under these principles, researchers can increase the reliability of their scholarly outputs.

- **CARE Model** (Carroll et al., 2020) foregrounds ethical considerations in data sharing, urging researchers to balance openness with respect for Indigenous rights through the principles of Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics.

Although these frameworks share the overarching goal of fostering reproducible science, they differ in their primary emphasis: FAIR focuses on research data management criteria, PRIMAD addresses various levels (or labels) of computational reproducibility, the provenance model captures data lineage and computational processes, and the Research Object approach bundles both digital and conceptual research artifacts. Meanwhile, TOP concentrates on publication standards, TRUST underscores repository reliability, and CARE highlights ethical engagement with diverse data sources. Collectively, they offer a comprehensive toolkit for transparent and reliable computational research practices. However, their successful implementation requires coordinated efforts spanning technical expertise, funding, and cultural shifts.

Finally, the preceding section discussed several practical frameworks and approaches that serve as a roadmap for implementing computational reproducibility applications in real-world research. The following two sections present these applications, ranging from research best practices and publication guidelines to technological platforms and tools that facilitate data management while ensuring transparency and usability.

5 Best Practices and Publishing

Major contributors to irreproducible computational research include the lack of sharing of research data and code, as well as inadequate documentation of key experimental details in publications (Pusztai et al., 2013; Mesnard & Barba, 2017; Kim et al., 2018). Although numerous efforts have introduced best practices, reporting checklists, and journal policies designed to address this problem, effectively these efforts enhance the reproducibility but do not reveal the whole pain (Gundersen et al., 2025). Nevertheless, it is essential to highlight the most prominent guidelines, best practices and initiatives given the evidence of their usefulness in enhancing computational reproducibility.

5.1 Best Practices

In computational science, adopting rigorous workflow practices, such as clear documentation, version control, automation of analyses, and open sharing of code and data, helps establish a “culture of reproducibility” (Sandve et al. 2013). In light of building this culture, a growing body of literature offers a multitude of guidance on best practices for computational reproducibility. Each of these resources underscores the importance of this culture. Good Enough Practices in Scientific Computing (Wilson et al., 2017) centres on simple, achievable steps, such as establishing a clear directory structure, adding a README file, and employing basic version control, so that researchers can readily adopt incremental improvements without chasing perfection. Ten Simple Rules for Reproducible Computational Research (Sandve et al., 2013) distils reproducibility into a straightforward checklist, covering the entire project lifecycle from data collection to publication and emphasising the need to record every step, version-control scripts, store raw data, and avoid manual data manipulation. The Practice of Reproducible Research (Kitzes et al., 2017) then illustrates these principles in action through 31 case studies that detail real-world workflows across multiple disciplines, showcasing how researchers use containers, collaboration protocols, and literate programming tools to maintain transparency and consistency throughout their projects. Five Pillars of Computational Reproducibility (Ziemann et al., 2023) complements these approaches with a practitioner-oriented framework that includes literate programming, version control with code sharing, computational environment control, comprehensive documentation, and persistent/FAIR data sharing. By incorporating these pillars, researchers can systematically ensure that all components of an analysis—from the raw data and code to the computing environment—are preserved and easily accessible for future use.

Despite differences in emphasis, each work converges on the same underlying principles: plan projects thoughtfully, document thoroughly, organise data and code consistently, and share materials openly. These best practices, when implemented consistently, help cultivate a culture of reproducibility that increases transparency, fosters collaboration, and ultimately strengthens scientific integrity across computational disciplines.

5.2 Checklists

In parallel across disciplines, reproducibility checklists have emerged as structured tools to support transparent, well-documented research workflows. Generally, a checklist is defined as a “list of action items, tasks or behaviours arranged in a consistent manner, which allows the evaluator to record the presence or absence of the individual items listed. Typically, each item is checked off as it is completed, verified, identified or answered, by placing a mark in a designated space.”, (Hales et al., 2008). Such checklists are conceptually aligned with the reporting guidelines catalogued in FAIRsharing, which specify the essential metadata required to interpret and reuse a study (Sansone et al., 2019). Collectively, these instruments embed best practices and lower barriers to reproducible science.

In biomedical and clinical fields, checklists improve reporting quality, as seen in AI research in dentistry (Schwendicke et al., 2021) and preclinical studies (Han et al., 2017). In computational domains, tailored checklists guide researchers to document software environments, model parameters, and data provenance, such as in metabolomics (Du et al., 2022), infectious disease modelling (Pokutnaya et al., 2023), and machine learning interoperability (Rahrooh et al., 2024). In ecology and molecular dynamics, checklists address metadata and simulation reproducibility (Feng et al., 2019; Pyzer-Knapp et al., 2022), while systems biology benefits from reproducibility scorecards (Waltemath et al., 2016). Plant pathology guidelines (Grünwald et al., 2024) similarly promote open access and standardisation.

5.3 Initiatives

The landscape of reproducibility initiatives is rich and multi-layered: global policies set the tone, agencies and institutions create incentives, community-driven standards or platforms provide part of the infrastructure, and educational programs cultivate the next generation of reproducible science (Nosek et al., 2020). At the **global** level, international organisations have set broad frameworks to encourage reproducible science. Notably, UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science (2021) calls on member states to adopt open-access policies for publications and data and to establish reproducibility standards as core principles of research (UNESCO, 2021). This UNESCO framework enshrines values like transparency, openness, and repeatability in

scientific work, aiming to make research findings more rigorously verified and accessible worldwide. In parallel, national research agencies have implemented policies to operationalise these principles. For example, the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) requires grant proposals to include detailed data management plans that describe how investigators will share well-documented datasets and code to support the reproducibility of their results⁷. Likewise, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) introduced a comprehensive Data Management and Sharing policy (2023) mandating that researchers plan for public data sharing “to enable transparency and reproducibility of research results”⁸. Such policies by major funding bodies embed reproducible practices as standard expectations in the research process.

Independent non-profit **organisations** and infrastructure providers have also been pivotal in promoting reproducibility across disciplines. The Centre for Open Science (COS)⁹, founded in 2013, explicitly centres its mission on increasing openness, integrity, and reproducibility in research. COS develops the Open Science Framework (OSF)¹⁰ that allows researchers to archive and share data, code, and workflows. It has led influential large-scale reproducibility initiatives, for instance, coordinating a multi-year Reproducibility Project in Psychology (Open Science Collaboration, 2015) as well as in Cancer Biology (Errington et al., 2014). In the publishing sphere, new journals such as ReScience C¹¹ have pioneered novel approaches to disseminating reproducible research. ReScience is an open-access, peer-reviewed journal specifically dedicated to publishing replication studies in computational science. In the scientific community domain, the Research Software Alliance (ReSA)¹² is an international coalition dedicated to promoting reproducibility and sustainability in research software. It champions best practices such as FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) (Barker et al., 2022) and coordinates global initiatives to improve how software and workflows are developed, documented, and shared.

⁷ <https://www.nsf.gov/funding/opportunities/computer-information-science-engineering-core-programs>

⁸ <https://libraryhelp.ucsf.edu/hc/en-us/articles/4488341760279-NIH-2023-Data-Management-and-Sharing-Policy>

⁹ <https://www.cos.io/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cos.io/products/osf>

¹¹ <https://rescience.github.io/>

¹² <https://www.researchsoft.org/>

Another critical development in recent years is the rise of grassroots reproducibility networks that span **institutions**. In the UK, the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)¹³ was formally launched in 2019 as a national, peer-led consortium to connect local efforts with system-wide change (UK Reproducibility Network Steering Committee, 2021). UKRN links a network of self-organised local reproducibility groups (often researchers at individual universities) with a coalition of universities and external stakeholders committed to research rigor. By coordinating bottom-up and top-down approaches, UKRN has become a model that has inspired similar national reproducibility networks in other countries, fostering an international community of practice around robust research. These networks emphasise that improving reproducibility is a shared responsibility, requiring support from funders, journals, and institutions alongside grassroots advocacy.

Within specific disciplines, countless tailored initiatives have emerged to address **domain-specific** barriers to reproducibility. In the social sciences, for example, the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences (BITSS) and the Centre for Effective Global Action (CEGA) launched the Social Science Reproduction Platform (SSRP)¹⁴, an openly licensed initiative that crowdsources and catalogues reproduction attempts by engaging students and researchers in systematically re-running original authors' code and analyses. The Annual Meetings of the American Economic Association (AEA) have also featured panels on reproducibility¹⁵. In the life sciences, the rapid advancement of single-cell genomics led to the formation of the Single-Cell Best Practices Consortium, which published a comprehensive set of community-agreed recommendations in 2023 for analysing single-cell RNA-seq and multi-omics data, ensuring standardised and reproducible workflows (Heumos et al., 2023). The physical sciences have similarly embraced open practices; notably, in 2020, the European Organisation for Nuclear Research, known as CERN¹⁶, adopted a shared open data policy to routinely release research-grade data—following an embargo period—so that findings can be independently verified and

¹³ <https://www.ukrn.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.socialsciencereproduction.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.aeaweb.org/news/cress-sept-21-2022>

¹⁶ <https://openscience.cern/open-data>

reused. In computer science and machine learning, the MLCommons¹⁷ consortium—a collaboration between academia and industry—introduced the MLPerf benchmark suite in 2018, which defines standardized tasks and evaluation criteria to enable reproducible and transparent comparisons of machine learning models and systems across platforms. Building on this, MLCommons released Croissant¹⁸ (often called CroissantML) in 2024—a community-driven schema.org-based metadata standard that renders ML datasets discoverable, interoperable and readily loadable across tools, thereby complementing MLPerf’s focus on model benchmarking.

Numerous **educational** initiatives have blossomed to equip researchers with the skills and mindsets for reproducible work. The Turing Way is an open handbook and training community that provides how-to guides on reproducible data science, covering topics from version control and testing to collaborative workflows and ethics (Turing Way Community 2021). The ELIXIR consortium’s RDMkit¹⁹ (Research Data Management Toolkit) offers domain-specific guidance on managing and sharing data in alignment with the FAIR principles. In the social sciences, Project TIER²⁰ (Teaching Integrity in Empirical Research) has developed a curriculum for incorporating reproducible research practices (such as creating replication documentation for every empirical project) into university courses and undergraduate theses. Software Carpentry, a long-standing initiative under The Carpentries organization²¹, delivers hands-on workshops teaching foundational coding and data skills to researchers with a strong emphasis on reproducibility. Similarly, Reproducibility for Everyone (Repro4Everyone)²² is a community-led initiative offering modular, scalable training materials and workshops designed to make reproducibility practical and approachable for researchers across all levels and disciplines. Many universities have also established Open Research or Reproducibility offices within libraries or research support units –

¹⁷ <https://mlcommons.org/>

¹⁸ <https://mlcommons.org/working-groups/data/croissant/>

¹⁹ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.projecttier.org/>

²¹ <https://carpentries.org/>

²² <https://www.repro4everyone.org/>

for instance, the University of Manchester’s Library, Open Research²³ and Research IT²⁴ departments host workshops on open and reproducible research methods. These training efforts stress the use of open-source tools and platforms and encourage researchers to share their work via an open research data platform such as Figshare²⁵, which mint Digital Object Identifiers²⁶ (DOIs) for datasets and software and thus facilitates proper citation and credit.

Meanwhile, in computer science education, Fund (2023) argues that reproducibility **training** must be woven more deeply into curricula to ensure robust and transparent computational workflows from the very start of students’ careers in academia as researchers or in industry as developers. Incorporating reproducibility content in the classroom can have a significant impact, as students not only gain valuable skills but also contribute artifacts and insights back to original authors and the broader research community; by serving as “reproducibility ambassadors,” they directly influence future colleagues and bolster reproducible practices across disciplines. As Pownall et al. (2023) note in a recent critical review, there remains a need for stronger evidence-based pedagogical methods and better evaluation of outcomes in teaching open and reproducible scholarship. Their critical review of literature surrounding the integration of open and reproducible scholarship into teaching and learning and its associated outcomes in students emphasised that while many resources exist, systematic assessment of how these teaching approaches improve students’ and researchers’ practices is still limited.

5.4 Publishing Practices

Computational reproducibility is increasingly supported by publishing practices such as badges, author checklists, and journal guidelines. These tools encourage researchers to share data/code, document methods thoroughly, and facilitate independent verification of results. Below, we

²³ <https://www.openresearch.manchester.ac.uk/>

²⁴ <https://research-it.manchester.ac.uk/>

²⁵ <https://figshare.com/>

²⁶ <https://www.doi.org/>

outline how badges, conference and committee checklists, and journal policies across disciplines are advancing transparent and reproducible research.

5.4.1 Badges for Open Science and Reproducibility

Several scholarly publishers have implemented badging systems to promote open-science and reproducible research practices (NISO, 2021). Badges are icons or labels awarded to publications that meet specific transparency criteria, serving both as incentives for authors to adhere to best practices and as visible markers for readers seeking to identify studies with shared resources or independently validated results. For instance, the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) introduced a standardised artifact review and badging policy²⁷, enabling authors to earn distinctions such as “Artifacts Available,” “Artifacts Evaluated,” and “Results Validated.”. In parallel, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) have also launched badging initiatives. IEEE Access, for example, is piloting a post-publication code peer review mechanism that awards badges²⁸ such as “Code Available” and “Code Reviewed.”

In addition to efforts by major publishers, the Centre for Open Science (COS) has developed a set of Open Science Badges²⁹—Open Data, Open Materials, and Preregistered—designed for use in any scholarly field. These badges reward authors who publicly share their research data, make experimental protocols or materials available, or preregister study designs and analysis plans. Complementing these initiatives of publishers and institutions, Heil et al. (2021) proposed a three-tiered badging system (Bronze, Silver, and Gold) to capture increasingly stringent reproducibility practices, particularly in machine learning research. Even a Bronze-level badge acknowledges foundational transparency, while Silver and Gold require progressive levels more documentation and automation.

²⁷ <https://www.acm.org/publications/policies/artifact-review-and-badging-current>

²⁸ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplorehelp/overview-of-ieee-xplore/about-content#reproducibility-badges>

²⁹ <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/badges>

5.4.2 Reproducibility Checklists in Conferences and Committees

Many scientific conferences and organisations now employ reproducibility checklists or guidelines that authors must follow during submission. These checklists act as structured reminders for authors to report crucial details and share necessary artifacts, thereby standardising the information needed to replicate studies. In computer science, major AI and machine learning conferences have led the way in adopting reproducibility checklists. For instance, NeurIPS³⁰,³¹ (Neural Information Processing Systems) introduced an “ML Reproducibility Checklist” in 2019 that authors had to complete with their submission (Pineau et al., 2021). This checklist prompts authors to disclose items such as a clear description of the model and algorithms, a link to source code (or pseudocode if code is not released), details of the computing environment, hyperparameter settings, training epochs, evaluation metrics, and whether the results were averaged over multiple runs, among other factors. It soon spread to other venues – the AAAI conference³² (Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence) implemented its reproducibility checklist starting in 2021, and ICLR³³ (International Conference on Learning Representations) and ICML³⁴ (International Conference on Machine Learning) followed suit with similar requirements. Notably, the checklist is submitted alongside the paper (often as a form) and, in some cases, even made available to reviewers, ensuring that referees can easily see whether the authors have provided code, data, and sufficient methodological details. Magnusson et al. (2023) analyses indicate these checklists are effective in the NLP (Natural Language Processing) papers. They found that submissions with more checklist “Yes” answers tended to be rated as more reproducible and even had higher acceptance rates.

In the life and biomedical sciences, reproducibility checklists are also emerging at conferences and workshops. Their calls for abstracts explicitly encourage the inclusion of URLs to code

³⁰ <https://www.cs.mcgill.ca/~jpineau/ReproducibilityChecklist.pdf>

³¹ <https://neurips.cc/Conferences/2019/CallForPapers>

³² <https://aaai.org/conference/aaai/aaai-25/aaai-25-reproducibility-checklist/>

³³ <https://iclr.cc/>

³⁴ <https://icml.cc/>

repositories and data; RECOMB³⁵ (Research in Computational Molecular Biology). Life science conferences are leveraging policies and submission guidelines (e.g. mandating a Data Availability statement or a Code Availability section) to instil reproducibility as a standard. These requirements mirror broader efforts in biology, such as reporting checklists for experimental design (e.g., ARRIVE³⁶ for animal studies, CONSORT³⁷ for clinical trials), which are now being adapted to computational work to ensure key computational steps are documented.

In computational physics and high-performance computing (HPC), the annual Super Computing (SC) conference has implemented a rigorous Reproducibility Initiative³⁸. SC introduced an Artifact Description (AD) and Artifact Evaluation (AE) Supplementary Data process, essentially a detailed checklist that authors fill out to describe their software environment, dependencies, hardware used, and steps to run their code. Their approach has now influenced other computational science venues (for example, the IEEE/ACM CCGrid³⁹ and SIGMOD⁴⁰ (The ACM Special Interest Group on Management of Data) conferences have similar artifact evaluation tracks). Overall, the SC conference's use of structured appendices and checklists ensures complete transparency of computational experiments and provides a template for independent researchers to rerun simulations or analyses in the domain. In social science, the American Economic Association bridge the gap between conferences and journals by enforcing community-wide standards: the AEA's journals (e.g., American Economic Review) will not publish a paper unless the data and code are submitted, documented, and verified by a data editor as part of the publication process⁴¹.

Beyond discipline-specific efforts, there are conferences devoted entirely to reproducibility and research integrity, which promulgate checklists/guidelines to a broad audience. The World

³⁵ <https://recomb.org/recomb2025/>

³⁶ <https://arriveguidelines.org/>

³⁷ <https://www.consort-spirit.org/>

³⁸ <https://sc25.supercomputing.org/program/papers/reproducibility-initiative/>

³⁹ <https://site.uit.no/ccgrid2025/artifacts/>

⁴⁰ <https://reproducibility.sigmod.org/>

⁴¹ <https://www.aeaweb.org/journals/data>

Conferences on Research Integrity (WCRI) have, for example, produced the Hong Kong Principles (HKPs)⁴² in 2019 – a set of high-level recommendations to reward responsible research practices, transparent reporting, open science, and reproducibility in research evaluation. Meanwhile, the Metascience conferences⁴³ bring together researchers, publishers, and policymakers from across fields to discuss how to improve the science of science. A key theme is reproducibility, sessions at Metascience conferences explicitly focus on building a research culture that supports replicability and on sharing successful interventions across domains. This cross-pollination is important: a checklist devised in one field (say, machine learning or sociology) can often be adapted to another, and forums like Metascience facilitate that exchange.

5.4.3 Journal Policies and Guidelines

Academic journals significantly shape research norms by implementing and enforcing policies that require open data, open code, and comprehensive methodological reporting. These policies often align with community checklists and badge systems, ensuring that reproducibility isn't just encouraged but required for publication. For example, PLOS⁴⁴ mandates public data sharing alongside a Data Availability Statement and may retract articles that fail to comply, thereby ensuring verifiability and transparency. GigaScience⁴⁵ takes this further by requiring authors to deposit all supporting data and source code in public repositories, often with containerised environments, for active verification during the peer-review process, effectively enabling “one-click” reproducibility. This approach, now mirrored by publishers such as Nature (Scientific Data⁴⁶), demonstrates a broader trend toward integrating reproducibility into the core publication workflow, setting a new standard for transparency and rigour across disciplines.

⁴² <https://www.wcrif.org/hong-kong-principles>

⁴³ <https://metascience.info/>

⁴⁴ <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/s/submission-guidelines>

⁴⁵ https://academic.oup.com/gigascience/pages/Author_Guidelines

⁴⁶ <https://www.nature.com/sdata/submission-guidelines>

6 Tools and Platforms Supporting Reproducibility

Having established the historical context and key definitions of reproducibility in computational science, as well as reviewed major conceptual frameworks (e.g., FAIR, PRIMAD, Research Objects), best practices and main initiatives, we can now shift focus to the practical domain of implementing reproducibility. If these frameworks offer a map of the theoretical landscape, then the tools and platforms described in this section represent the practical technologies that guide researchers toward reproducible outcomes.

6.1 Metadata Standards

Metadata standards provide structured descriptions of research data, methods, and software, serving as the “glue” of reproducibility by capturing essential context and provenance (Leipzig et al., 2021). By ensuring that key research details are documented in a consistent format, these standards enable other researchers to locate, understand, and replicate the components needed to repeat an experiment. Leipzig et al. (2021) propose categorising metadata standards based on their function and role in the computational analysis workflow, and these categories map naturally onto the PRIMAD model (Freire et al., 2016), see section 4.2. Specifically, metadata about raw data and intermediates (e.g., MIAME; (Brazma et al., 2001)) aligns with the Data (D) dimension, while metadata describing scripts and executables (e.g., CodeMeta⁴⁷) corresponds primarily to Implementation (I) and sometimes Platform (P) if it specifies runtime environments. Metadata for statistical approaches or rationale (e.g., MLflow (Zaharia et al., 2018) captures the Method (M) dimension, whereas metadata that tracks pipeline dependencies and deliverables, including provenance (e.g., CWL (Crusoe et al., 2022), spans Method (M), Platform (P), and potentially Actor (A) when workflow ownership or authorship is recorded. Finally, publication-focused metadata (e.g., Dublin Core (Weibel et al. 1998)) supports the Research Objective (R) by encapsulating the study’s purpose and context and also covers Actor (A) by identifying authors and contributors.

⁴⁷ <https://codemeta.github.io/>

Reproducibility can't fit into a one-size solution (Stewart et al., 2021). Consequently, researchers adopt different standards to make their datasets, code, and workflows more findable, interoperable, and reusable, thereby directly supporting reproducibility (Wilkinson et al., 2016). However, as highlighted in the review by Leipzig et al. (2021), the proliferation of diverse standards for datasets, tools, pipelines, and reports can complicate integration, and many researchers struggle to implement extensive schemas in routine practice. Approaches like Research Objects (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022) aim to consolidate various metadata elements of a research workflow into a single package, promoting a future in which multiple standards can cooperate seamlessly (see sections 4.4 and 6.7).

6.2 Provenance Capture Tools

Provenance capture tools record the history of computations, encompassing the sequence of steps, data transformations, and dependencies that lead to the result, thereby enabling researchers to understand and re-run analyses under the same conditions (Pimentel et al., 2019). By automatically logging which actions were taken, on which data, and with which software, such tools create a transparent “map” of how outcomes are produced, which is crucial for reproducibility (Moreau, 2011). A variety of approaches exist; some operate at the operating system level (capturing file accesses and system calls) to remain language-agnostic, while others instrument specific environments or workflow engines. For instance, ReproZip traces system calls to bundle code, data, and the full environment into a single portable package (Chirigati et al., 2016), whereas noWorkflow instruments Python scripts to record function calls, library versions, and intermediate results automatically, without requiring a workflow language (Pimentel et al., 2019). Workflow management systems (as we will discuss later in section 6.4), such as Galaxy or Nextflow, also maintain built-in provenance logs, storing each task’s inputs and outputs in a workflow graph that can be inspected or replayed. The benefits of such dedicated provenance capture are manifold: researchers can debug experiments by examining intermediate steps, detect discrepancies if results do not match, and even reuse the recorded process by applying it to new datasets (Murta et al., 2015). Nonetheless, challenges remain. High-detail provenance can become unwieldy and difficult to interpret, whereas overly minimal records may omit key

information, rendering exact reruns impossible; tools like noWorkflow partially address this by allowing users to choose granularity (Pimentel et al., 2019). Additionally, provenance-capture technologies often impose a learning curve, and many scientists still rely on ad-hoc scripts, prompting the emergence of approaches like YesWorkflow that retrospectively annotate such scripts to infer provenance, though typically only for single runs (Pimentel et al., 2019). Recent efforts to integrate provenance with other reproducibility infrastructures—e.g., ProvBook embedding execution-order tracking in Jupyter notebooks (Samuel & König-Ries, 2022) highlight the push toward automated reproducibility pipelines. Further standardisation, for instance via W3C PROV (see section 4.3), is seen as critical to fostering broader adoption and interoperability.

In parallel with these capture tools, the literature notes that fully leveraging provenance often requires tying it to other key artifacts: data, code, containers, and workflow descriptions, so that an entire analysis chain can be packaged and shared (Chirigati et al., 2016; Pimentel et al., 2017). This is where approaches like Research Objects (RO) come to the fore, enabling researchers to embed provenance metadata in a coherent bundle alongside scripts, data, environment specifications, and publication details (see sections 4.4 and 6.7).

6.3 Containerization and Virtual Environments

Containerization and virtual environment tools address the reproducibility of the computational environment, ensuring that software dependencies and operating system (OS) configurations are consistent. In computational research, one common cause of irreproducibility is environmental drift: code runs on the author’s machine but fails on another due to different library versions, OS, or hardware. Containers, such as those created by Docker (Merkel, 2014) or Singularity (Kurtzer et al., 2017), solve this by encapsulating all required components in a “portable image”; containers mitigate this challenge, enabling others to reconstruct a study’s environment precisely, even years later, so long as the container itself and the means to run it are preserved (Nüst et al., 2020). Boettiger (2015) demonstrated Docker’s utility for reproducible research by showing that an entire R analysis, with all required packages and system libraries, could be shipped as a Docker image and run on any computer with Docker, yielding identical results. For instance, a bioinformatics pipeline requiring Python with specific libraries can be bundled into a Docker

image or Singularity container, ensuring that any researcher, regardless of their host system, can replicate the pipeline's execution and results (Kurtzer et al., 2017). This isolation also prevents interference from other software installed on the host machine, reducing inconsistencies. Beyond Docker, Singularity is particularly well-suited for HPC and academic clusters, allowing users without root privileges to run container images (Kurtzer et al., 2017). Many workflow systems and services, such as CWL (Crusoe et al., 2022), Nextflow (Di Tommaso et al., 2017), and Binder (Jupyter et al., 2018), integrate container references directly into their pipelines, ensuring each step runs with the necessary dependencies.

Besides containers, lighter-weight virtual environments also contribute to reproducibility by allowing project-specific dependency management. For example, the `conda`⁴⁸ environment where the term "conda" has since evolved to encompass an entire open-source packaging ecosystem and philosophy. For instance, a researcher can provide an `environment.yml` file listing exact package versions; another user can create the same Conda environment and thereby replicate the library stack used in the analysis. Containers isolate an entire operating system environment, bundling the application, its dependencies, and a minimal OS layer, ensuring consistent execution across different machines (Merkel, 2014). In contrast, virtual environments generally manage only application-level libraries (e.g., Python packages) within the same host OS and do not include a separate operating system layer.

However, containers come with their complexities: writing a Docker file demands careful attention to provenance, such as specifying the base image and build steps, and ensuring the image is stored in a reliable repository (Nüst et al., 2020). Longevity poses another hurdle, since repositories may not persist indefinitely, and future systems might require rebuilding or migrating container images to remain functional. Despite these concerns, the literature underscores containerization's pivotal role in reproducibility. Journals increasingly encourage authors to provide containers or cloud-based VM images alongside their code and data, thus addressing the "it works on my machine" problem (Kurtzer et al., 2017). Virtual machines like

⁴⁸ <https://conda.org/>

VirtualBox⁴⁹ or AWS⁵⁰ (Amazon Web Services) images offered an earlier strategy with similar benefits, but containers are generally more lightweight and flexible. Combined with version-controlled code and stable data, containers yield self-contained research packages that can be shared, cited, and re-run (e.g. DockStore (Yuen et al., 2021)), fulfilling a major requirement of reproducible science (Boettiger, 2015). The remaining gaps revolve around adoption (many researchers need training to use Docker or Singularity effectively) and integration (linking container images to DOIs or capturing their provenance). Yet as tools and standards evolve, containers are becoming a de facto best practice for ensuring analyses run consistently across machines, bridging the gap between local experimentation and broad-scale reproducibility.

6.4 Workflow Management Systems

Computational workflows are prevalent across scientific domains as it is expanded to include a wide variety of interdependent computational tasks and data transfers (Suter et al., 2025). Workflow Management Systems (WMS) automate the design, execution, and monitoring of multi-step computational pipelines, thereby reducing human error and easing the sharing of complex analyses (Deelman et al., 2015; Zheng et al., 2015). Among the more than 300 workflow management systems⁵¹ (Amstutz et al., 2024), ranging from the past (e.g. Taverna (Hull et al., 2006)) to the current (e.g. Galaxy⁵², Pegasus⁵³, Nextflow⁵⁴ and Snakemake⁵⁵). All aim to codify an analytical process. Once researchers define their workflow as a set of tasks with specified dependencies, the WMS ensures each step is run in the correct order, captures provenance logs of inputs/outputs, and can often incorporate container images for each stage, thus providing an additional layer of reproducibility and manageability. For instance, Galaxy includes histories of every analysis in a web-based interface, making it possible to “click to rerun” an entire pipeline with the same parameters and dataset versions (Zheng et al., 2015; Galaxy Community, 2022).

⁴⁹ <https://www.virtualbox.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://aws.amazon.com/>

⁵¹ <https://s.apache.org/existing-workflow-systems>

⁵² <https://galaxyproject.org/>

⁵³ <https://pegasus.isi.edu/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

⁵⁵ <https://snakemake.github.io/>

However, WMS also have challenges: they can require significant setup and specialised expertise, which may deter researchers from disciplines lacking extensive computational training (Zheng et al., 2015). Additionally, many WMS originally used proprietary or system-specific formats, impeding workflow portability.

On the other hand, as part of the growing of an ecosystem of services for fair computational workflows (Wilkinson et al., 2025) aimed at reducing duplication of effort, fostering collaboration, and promoting best practices for reproducible computational research, the WorkflowHub⁵⁶ (Gustafsson et al., 2024) serves as a centralised registry for workflows and workflow run records (e.g. Galaxy or Nextflow workflows), enabling researchers to discover, share, and reuse existing pipelines across different disciplines.

Workflow Management Systems form the backbone of reproducible workflow practices. It automates and tracks workflow execution across various platforms. Combined with containerization (e.g., Docker, Singularity) and data/code versioning, they allow research teams to publish fully reproducible pipelines. The key issues going forward are ensuring usability, standard convergence, and adoption across different scientific communities, so that the formal capture of workflows (rather than unstructured scripts) becomes the norm, and complex analyses can be replicated anywhere without ambiguity (Crusoe et al., 2022; Pimentel et al., 2017).

6.5 Version Control Systems

Version Control Systems (VCS) have become nearly ubiquitous in computational research, with the reproducibility literature consistently highlighting their role in tracking iterative changes to code and scripts (Sandve et al., 2013; Wilson et al., 2014; Pimentel et al., 2019; Akhlaghi et al., 2021; Ziemann et al., 2023). Tools like Git⁵⁷ enable researchers to maintain a comprehensive history of code and documentation, making it possible to retrieve the exact version that produced

⁵⁶ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

⁵⁷ <https://git-scm.com/>

a given result. Moreover, platforms such as GitHub⁵⁸ address one of the major barriers to reproducibility, unavailable source code (Baker, 2016), by facilitating collaboration and open sharing. Beyond code, VCS adoption has expanded to data and computational environments: Git LFS (Abildskov, 2020), Git-Theta (Kandpal et al., 2023), and DVC (Kuprieiev et al., 2021) extend version control to large datasets and machine learning models. Ram (2013) argued that Git can “facilitate greater reproducibility and increased transparency in science,” supporting reuse, error detection, and peer verification. However, despite this potential, many scientists still lack formal training in VCS tools (Wilson, 2014). While VCS captures code evolution, it does not inherently document runtime environments, prompting the complementary use of containerization. Nevertheless, the cultural shift toward open-source code in science, supported by robust VCS platforms, continues to drive progress in reproducibility and accountability (Peng, 2011).

6.6 Computational Notebooks

Computational notebooks are interactive documents that merge code, results, and narrative text (Shen, 2014), thereby exemplifying the literate programming paradigm described by Knuth (1984): “The main idea is to treat a program as a piece of literature, addressed to human beings rather than to a computer.” By interweaving human-readable explanations with machine-executable code, notebooks provide a powerful means to ensure transparency, a principle central to reproducibility (Pimentel et al., 2019). They have thus been widely adopted in data science and numerous scientific fields, particularly via Jupyter notebooks, which enable an exploratory iterative workflow (Pimentel et al., 2019). As Rowe et al. (2020) point out, notebooks significantly enhance teaching open software operations, applying novel methods, promoting interactive and exploratory analysis, and producing replicable, reproducible, and transparent research.

Nonetheless, sharing a notebook alone may not guarantee reproducibility unless the computational environment (“Platform”) is also captured (Grüning et al., 2018). Moreover, large-scale studies reveal that many Jupyter notebooks on GitHub exhibit additional issues such as

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/>

inconsistent execution order, missing definitions, or dependency on specific execution histories (Pimentel et al., 2019). Best-practice guidelines have emerged to address these pitfalls (Rule et al. 2019; Pimentel et al., 2019), including versioning the notebooks, ensuring linear execution, and pairing them with an environment specification. This underscores the utility of containers and version control, as well as comprehensive packaging approaches (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022) that can bundle interactive documents and their corresponding environments, thereby supporting a more robust and complete reproducible workflow.

6.7 Research Packaging Tools

In 2010, the notion of the Research Object (RO) (Bechhofer et al., 2010) was introduced to fulfil the evolving requirements of research publishing by offering a systematic, semantic encapsulation mechanism for all related elements of scientific studies, see section 4.4. Later, in 2020, Willis and Stodden emphasised that a uniform mechanism for packaging research artifacts is essential to advance reproducible publishing, arguing that science requires more than the mere exchange of papers (De Roure, 2014). They proposed the concept of assessable computational research artifacts, bundles that not only contain all the information required for computational reproduction but also include verification and review metadata, regardless of where the metadata is hosted.

Since the introduction of the Research Object concept, numerous initiatives have emerged to strengthen the reproducibility of scientific data and workflows, each employing distinct strategies to package, preserve, and re-execute research artifacts. Some of these efforts explicitly align with “Research Object” principles or metadata models for general scientific contexts, such as Sciunits⁵⁹ (That et al., 2017), WholeTale⁶⁰ (Chard et al., 2020), and RO-Crate⁶¹ (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022), while others are specialised for particular domains, for example, the BioCompute Object⁶² (Simonyan et al., 2017; Alterovitz et al., 2018) in bioinformatics.

⁵⁹ <https://sciunit.readthedocs.io/en/latest/setup.html>

⁶⁰ <https://wholetale.org/>

⁶¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁶² <https://docs.biocomputeobject.org/>

However, some reproducibility tools draw inspiration from the Research Object concept in their designs without being formally labelled as “Research Objects.” For example, ReproZip⁶³ (Chirigati et al., 2016) captures the complete computational environment of an experiment, including code, data, libraries, and dependencies, into a portable, self-contained .rpz package, facilitating seamless reproduction across different systems. Another example is the Compute Capsule⁶⁴, developed by Code Ocean, which encapsulates code, data, execution environments, and results into a managed, cloud-based container to enable effortless sharing, re-execution, and publication of computational research. On the other hand, Sciunits offers a model-based method for describing computational components (That et al., 2017) by creating reusable “research object” containers that integrate an experiment’s code, data, and software environment. WholeTale further extends packaging concepts by including narrative documentation and publishing capabilities (Chard et al., 2020). It encapsulates data, code, container images, and explanatory text into a single, standards-based package, which can then be published with a DOI for citation.

The BioCompute Object (BCO) (Simonyan et al., 2017; Alterovitz et al., 2018), formalized as an IEEE 2791-2020⁶⁵ Standard for Bioinformatics Analyses Generated by High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS), encapsulates a standardized JSON description of computational workflows related to genomic pipeline generation, execution, and communication. BCO schema defines seven “domains” describing the workflow and specifies an eighth domain (“extension_domain”) as a space for additional structured information or metadata not defined in the BioCompute schema. This extension allows BCO to include specialised metadata, ensuring that researchers can fully document their bioinformatics pipelines in a transparent and reusable format. Each BCO consists of three top-level fields (a unique identifier, schema version reference, and hash value) and eight domains. Five domains—Usability, Provenance, Execution, Description, and Input/Output—are mandatory, while the Error, Parametric, and Extension domains are optional. Extension domain” as a space for additional structured information or metadata not defined in the BioCompute schema. This extension allows BCO to include specialised metadata, ensuring

⁶³ <https://www.reprozip.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://codeocean.com/blog/what-is-a-compute-capsule>

⁶⁵ <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2791/7337/>

that researchers can fully document their bioinformatics pipelines in a transparent and reusable format. These elements collectively describe the workflow steps, inputs and outputs, computational environment, provenance, and usage context.

Similarly, RO-Crate provides a flexible mechanism for embedding metadata describing any segment of the research workflow within a central metadata file (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022). Such extensibility is crucial for accommodating the vast heterogeneity of computational experiments, enabling researchers to integrate multiple standards and preserve the contextual details needed to reproduce complex analyses. RO-Crate is a community-driven specification that uses JSON-LD and schema.org vocabularies to describe research contents in a human- and machine-readable manner, facilitating discoverability, metadata interoperability, and long-term accessibility. These contents may include the study's contextual entities (e.g., researchers and their affiliations) as well as non-contextual entities (e.g., datasets, scripts, execution environments, and other digital artifacts). Because the specification is lightweight, domain agnostic, Linked-Data-based, and community-governed, RO-Crate has emerged as a promising instrument for standardised, transparent, and machine-actionable research documentation (Semmelrock et al. 2025). It has been adopted across multiple scientific fields⁶⁶, including the life sciences, social sciences, and physical sciences, each harnessing different subsets of the specification to meet its respective reproducibility goals.

However, while research packaging tools provide powerful mechanisms to enhance reproducibility, they can also pose challenges. Packages can become excessively large, complicating storage, sharing, and archiving. They also risk including proprietary, sensitive, or copyrighted materials, which can create legal and ethical barriers to open dissemination. Additionally, long-term reproducibility remains uncertain, as future environmental drift, obsolete software, or decommissioned services may hinder re-execution of packages. Technical complexity poses another challenge, as many tools require significant expertise to use effectively. Moreover, incomplete capture of dependencies, lack of standardisation across platforms, and metadata inconsistencies can undermine the intended reproducibility. Finally, preparing

⁶⁶ https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/use_cases

comprehensive, high-quality packages demands considerable effort, yet researchers often receive little formal recognition for this work, limiting broader adoption.

Despite these limitations, research packaging tools remain an essential strategy for advancing reproducibility, particularly when integrated with repository platforms (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare) or continuous integration services. Such integrations enable researchers to store, manage, and share self-contained computational experiments, thereby bridging the gap between theoretical reproducibility and the practical challenges of re-executing another researcher's code (Chard et al., 2020).

6.8 Data Management and Sharing Platforms

Sharing research data through robust repositories is widely recognised as a cornerstone of computational reproducibility (Wilkinson et al., 2016). As outlined by Steinhart and Skinner (2024), research data repositories can be categorised into several primary types: disciplinary repositories, generalist repositories, institutional repositories, project-specific repositories, and research paper supplements. Each plays a distinct role in supporting reproducibility, depending on its scope, infrastructure, and the standards adopted within its research community. Common features that enhance reproducibility across repository types include persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs or accession numbers), metadata standards, long-term preservation policies, integration with reproducible workflows, and access to raw data and code (Lin et al., 2020; The Turing Way Community, 2021; Wilkinson et al., 2016). However, the implementation of these features varies significantly across repository types, leading to distinct strengths, limitations, and trade-offs (Steinhart & Skinner, 2024).

Disciplinary (domain-specific) repositories serve specific research communities by enforcing field-specific metadata standards, data formats, and documentation practices that promote consistency and reuse. For instance, ICPSR⁶⁷ supports reproducibility in the social sciences by

⁶⁷ <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/pages/about/data-stewardship.html>

requiring detailed documentation and codebooks, while GenBank ⁶⁸ (Genomics), DataOne ⁶⁹ (Earth and Environmental Data) and MAST ⁷⁰ (Astronomy) enable reuse through standardised submission protocols and persistent accession identifiers. Similarly, repositories such as PANGAEA ⁷¹ (earth and environmental sciences) and RePEc ⁷² (economics) promote transparency by linking data to peer-reviewed publications and supporting domain-specific discovery tools. These repositories are often curated by domain experts, ensuring that the data remains meaningful and interoperable over time. While their specialisation ensures a high level of reproducibility within their communities, it can also limit interoperability or data discovery across disciplines.

On the other hand, generalist repositories offer broad accessibility to researchers across disciplines and domains. Examples include Zenodo, Figshare, Dryad, Harvard Dataverse, OSF, and Mendeley Data. Barbosa et al. (2022) described them as “store and preserve a wide variety of data types and research outputs and usually accept data regardless of the type, format, content, disciplinary focus, or research institution affiliation”. These generalist platforms typically assign DOIs, support version control, provide basic metadata templates, and ensure long-term preservation of datasets (Stall et al., 2023). Zenodo, for example, integrates with GitHub to archive code repositories and mint DOIs for each release, an especially valuable feature for capturing and preserving computational workflows. Dryad emphasises curation and is often integrated with journal publishing workflows, while OSF allows researchers to collaboratively manage versioned research projects and link data with analysis tools. Although these platforms may not support domain-specific metadata standards or in-depth curation, their inclusivity and flexibility make them especially valuable for interdisciplinary research and for fields that lack established domain repositories.

⁶⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>

⁶⁹ <https://www.dataone.org/>

⁷⁰ <https://archive.stsci.edu/>

⁷¹ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

⁷² <http://repec.org/>

Institutional repositories, such as Harvard Dataverse, are typically managed by universities or research libraries and provide long-term archiving and DOI assignment for research outputs generated by affiliated scholars. These repositories support reproducibility by ensuring that research outputs, including data from smaller or unpublished studies, are preserved, citable, and accessible. However, their visibility and discoverability are often limited outside the hosting institution, and they may lack the metadata specificity of disciplinary repositories. On the other hand, project-specific repositories are designed to support large-scale research programs by hosting curated datasets, associated software, and sometimes full computational environments. For example, NASA's Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs) provide long-term access to Earth science data. At the same time, the CERN Open Data Portal enables full-stack reproducibility by archiving data alongside virtual machines and documentation used in high-energy physics experiments. These repositories offer tailored support for complex data workflows but often depend on sustained funding and infrastructure from the originating project or institution.

Research paper supplements, typically hosted on journal websites (e.g., GigaScience, PLOS), allow authors to submit datasets and code as supplementary materials to accompany their articles. While this ensures co-publication and easy access, supplements frequently lack persistent identifiers, structured metadata, and preservation guarantees, limiting their long-term utility for reproducibility (Steinhart & Skinner, 2024). For this reason, many journals now recommend or require authors to deposit materials in certified external repositories and reference them within the article.

Additionally, with the rapidly increasing adoption of machine learning models, a prominent hosting and collaboration platform for the AI/ML community, the Hugging Face Hub⁷³ offers Git-backed, versioned repositories for models and datasets. Standardised Model Cards and Dataset Cards document provenance, assumptions, and intended use, while environment specifications

⁷³ <https://huggingface.co/>

and evaluation tools support reproducible workflows and comparable results; thereby enhancing computational reproducibility.

Together, these repository types form a complementary ecosystem for reproducible research. Disciplinary repositories offer depth, trust, and domain-specific metadata; generalist and institutional repositories provide flexibility, inclusivity, and broad access; project-specific repositories enable full-stack reproducibility for complex research infrastructures; and journal supplements continue to play a transitional role in linking publications with supporting materials. By understanding these trade-offs, researchers can make informed decisions about where and how to share their data, ensuring that their computational results are not only preserved but are verifiable, discoverable, sustainable, and reusable by others.

6.9 Tools and Platforms Across PRIMAD Model

Recognising that many tools address multiple aspects of the research lifecycle, we can better understand their specific roles by referencing the PRIMAD model (Freire et al., 2016), which categorises computational research components into Platform, Research Objective, Implementation, Method, Actor, and Data (see section 4.2). Table 3 maps key reproducibility tools to the relevant PRIMAD dimensions, highlighting where each tool offers its greatest support. Typically, the real-world reproducible research uses a combination of these tools because reproducibility touches on all six PRIMAD elements. However, most tools usually relate to the technical aspects of a computational experiment, such as the environment, code, data or workflow. As a result, some often overlook the non-technical elements, like the study's goal (Research Objective) and the roles or contributions of the research team (Actor). Here, the Research Objects (RO) framework fills this gap by enabling the integration of both technical and non-technical (conceptual) information within a single "package" (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2022). This approach is able to describe each tool's function clearly, while also capturing essential contextual details, such as the study's purpose and contributor roles, thus offering a more comprehensive view of the entire research study.

Computational Reproducibility		Tools and Platforms								
PRIMAD Model		Research Packaging Tools	Metadata Standards	Provenance Capture Tools	Containerization	Virtual Environments	Version Control Systems	Workflow Management Systems	Computational Notebooks	Research Repositories
P	Platform	✓	✓		✓	✓				
R	Research Objective	✓	✓						✓	✓
I	Implementation	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓
M	Method	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	
A	Actor	✓	✓	✓			✓			✓
D	Data	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 3. Mapping Reproducibility Tools to The PRIMAD Model. This table shows how various reproducibility tools align with the PRIMAD dimensions: Platform, Research Objective, Implementation, Method, Actor, and Data.

7 Conclusion

This review mapped the computational reproducibility ecosystem across four areas—(1) foundations and definitions, (2) conceptual frameworks and principles, (3) best practices and publishing, and (4) tools and platforms—and used the PRIMAD model (Freire et al., 2016) to classify tools along the dimensions of Platform, Research Objective, Implementation, Method, Actor, and Data, clarifying how computational experiments through research life cycle used different tools.

Across the literature, one conclusion is consistent: reproducibility “takes a village.” Infrastructure and tooling are necessary but insufficient without aligned incentives, publication norms, and community culture (Peng 2011; Goble 2013; Nosek 2019; Borgman and Bvilaourne 2022; Freire 2023; Goble 2025). Peng (2011) underscored the twin barriers of infrastructure and culture; Nosek (2019) foregrounds misaligned incentives and the need for policy-driven culture change; Freire (2023) notes that the adoption of reproducibility involves tools, training, the dissemination of best practices, as well as incentives and enforcement from related parties and policymakers.

Goble (2025) likewise emphasised that advancements in infrastructure and metadata middleware must go hand in hand with changes in community culture, such as giving credit for reproducible work. Finally, Borgman & Bourne (2022) emphasise that achieving data sharing and reproducibility requires coordinated, multi-stakeholder action across researchers, institutions, journals, funders, and infrastructure providers.

These challenges persist as each computational paradigm: data-intensive (Hey, 2009) and AI-driven (Ioannidis, 2024), adds complexity faster than socio-technical practices evolve. Against this backdrop, the literature stresses that transparency is the reliable baseline safeguard: reproducibility is an essential means, not an end. The Dagstuhl 16041 report puts it plainly: “reproducibility in its various forms ... is never a goal in itself” (Freire et al., 2016), and the U.S. National Academies likewise argue that reproducibility and replicability are not, in and of themselves, the end goals of science (NASEM, 2019).

Taken together, the review motivates a pragmatic agenda: set a minimum transparency baseline; adopt tooling; and align evaluation, funding, and publishing incentives with credit for reusable artifacts. Only then can the computational reproducibility ecosystem scale with the pace of science.

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